

Synthesis, Spectral, Thermal, Electrical and Antimicrobial Studies of some Complexes of α -Oximinoacetoacet-*o/p*-chloroanilide- β -thiosemicarbazone

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Manuscript received 2 March 1993, accepted 16 November 1993

Solid complexes of α -oximinoacetoacet-*o/p*-chloroanilide- β -thiosemicarbazone (OOCATS)/(OAPCATS) with Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} and UO_2^{II} have been prepared and characterised by elemental analyses, conductivity, differential scanning calorimetry, thermogravimetric analyses and infrared and electronic spectral data in conjunction with magnetic susceptibility measurements. They have also been tested for their antibacterial activities.

Although ligands having oxygen and nitrogen as the donor atoms are by far the most studied, the interest in sulphur donor chelating agents has grown over the years and the number of chemical studies in this area has increased considerably¹. The interest in complexes of these ligand systems now covers a full gamut of areas ranging from general considerations to metal-sulphur bonding and electron delocalisation in transition metal complexes to potential biological activity and practical applications^{2,3}. Thiosemicarbazones comprise a well known group of nitrogen and sulphur donors which have been extensively used for complex formation in the recent past^{3,4}. The present communication reports α -oximinoacetoacet-*o*-chloroanilide- β -thiosemicarbazone (OOCATS), α -oximinoacetoacet-*p*-chloroanilide- β -thiosemicarbazone (OAPCATS) and their complexes with Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Mn^{II} , Hg^{II} , Cd^{II} and UO_2^{II} metal ions. The ligands and their metal chelates have also been tested for their antimicrobial properties⁵.

Results and Discussion

The magnetic, analytical and electrical data of the metal chelates are presented in Table 1. Elemental analyses of the complexes indicate 1 : 1 stoichiometry.

Magnetic and reflectance spectra : The Ni^{II}

complexes are diamagnetic in nature indicating that they have square-planar configuration. The reflectance spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes exhibit two bands at 14 950–14 980 and 20 160–20 210 cm^{-1} which are assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ transitions respectively, in favour of the square-planar structure⁶. The Co^{II} complexes show magnetic moment values of 4.33–4.37 B.M. indicating the presence of three unpaired electrons and also suggests the tetrahedral structure for them. The reflectance spectra of the Co^{II} complexes exhibit three bands at 8 870–8 940, 15 250–15 390 and 23 400–24 810 cm^{-1} which are assigned to ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(F)$, ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ and charge transfer transitions respectively, for tetrahedral geometry⁷. The magnetic moment (5.44–5.46 B.M.) for the Mn^{II} complexes is lower than the spin-only value (5.92 B.M.) which may be due to partial aerial oxidation of Mn^{II} to Mn^{III} during synthesis. The reflectance spectra of the Mn^{II} complexes exhibit three bands at 16 400–16 700, 19 500–19 630 and 23 485–24 565 cm^{-1} which are assigned to the ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}({}^4G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g, {}^4A_{1g}({}^4G)$ transitions respectively, considering an octahedral symmetry. The reflectance spectra of the dioxouranium(VI) chelates exhibit two bands at 20 815–21 555 and 24 610–24 690 cm^{-1} which are assigned to the ${}^1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow {}^3\pi_u$ and charge transfer transitions respectively, for octahedral

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE CHELATES

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.	σ $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$	Activation energy eV
	M	N	S			
OAOCATS (Yellowish white)	—	17.81 (17.85)	10.15 (10.20)	—	5.0×10^{-14}	0.114
Ni-OAOCATS (Brown)	15.84 (15.85)	15.05 (15.12)	8.63 (8.64)	Diamag.	6.73×10^{-13}	0.058
Co-OAOCATS (Dark brown)	15.88 (15.90)	15.07 (15.11)	8.60 (8.63)	4.37	7.55×10^{-13}	0.143
Zn-OAOCATS (Yellow)	17.30 (17.33)	14.81 (14.85)	8.47 (8.48)	Diamag.	3.11×10^{-12}	0.115
Mn-OAOCATS.2H ₂ O (Brown)	13.58 (13.64)	13.89 (13.90)	7.92 (7.94)	5.44	1.7×10^{-13}	0.072
Cd-OAOCATS (Dull yellow)	26.45 (26.50)	13.11 (13.20)	7.47 (7.54)	Diamag.	2.85×10^{-12}	0.059
Hg-OAOCATS (Yellow)	39.11 (39.15)	10.85 (10.93)	6.24 (6.24)	Diamag.	5.41×10^{-13}	0.045
UO ₂ -OAOCATS.2H ₂ O (Brick red)	43.65 (43.71)	9.01 (9.06)	5.17 (5.18)	Diamag.	3.71×10^{-14}	0.087
OAPCATS (Off white)	—	17.82 (17.85)	10.16 (10.20)	—	1.7×10^{-12}	0.310
Ni-OAPCATS (Chocolate)	15.83 (15.85)	15.07 (15.12)	8.63 (8.64)	Diamag.	6.13×10^{-13}	0.117
Co-OAPCATS (Brown)	15.88 (15.90)	15.09 (15.11)	8.59 (8.63)	4.33	5.15×10^{-14}	0.115
Zn-OAPCATS (Yellow)	17.31 (17.33)	14.82 (14.85)	8.46 (8.48)	Diamag.	2.61×10^{-13}	0.130
Mn-OAPCATS.2H ₂ O (Dark brown)	13.60 (13.64)	13.85 (13.90)	7.90 (7.94)	5.46	1.80×10^{-12}	0.080
Cd-OAPCATS (Dull yellow)	26.47 (26.50)	13.15 (13.20)	7.50 (7.54)	Diamag.	4.99×10^{-13}	0.112
Hg-OAPCATS (Light yellow)	39.10 (39.15)	10.87 (10.93)	6.20 (6.24)	Diamag.	9.48×10^{-12}	0.107
UO ₂ -OAPCATS.2H ₂ O (Brick red)	43.63 (43.71)	9.00 (9.06)	5.14 (5.18)	Diamag.	2.31×10^{-12}	0.114

stereoche-mistry⁸. The Zn^{II}, UO₂^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are found to be diamagnetic⁹.

Infrared spectra : Complete assignment of all the absorptions of the ligands is not attempted here, only a prominent few, essential for the determination of bonding sites in the ligands, are assigned. The absence of absorption due to S—H stretching at about 2 570 cm⁻¹ indicates that the ligand remains in thioketo form (I) at least in the solid state¹⁰. However, in solution, the existence of thioketo (I) and thioenol (II) tautomerism may be likely

The C=O stretching frequency appears at about 1 665 cm⁻¹ as a very strong absorption¹¹. It

is found to be shifted to higher wavenumbers by about 10 cm^{-1} in the metal chelates which may be traced to the breaking of hydrogen bond between C=O and N-OH moiety. This replacement of hydrogen bond is further supported by the disappearance of ligand peak ($2\ 700\text{--}2\ 800\text{ cm}^{-1}$) after complex formation. The characteristic absorption due to N-O stretching of N-OH moiety in ligand occurs at about 950 cm^{-1} . This disappears in the complexes and a new band at $1\ 315\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assigned to N-O stretching appears¹². This suggests the presence of M-N-O bonding. In comparison with the comparable molecules the frequency at about 860 cm^{-1} in the ligands may be attributed to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$. On complexation, this band disappears and a new band around 665 cm^{-1} appears assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{S}}$. This observation indicates the presence of M-S-C bonding in the metal complexes. The use of the absorption due to C=N stretching in identifying the bonding site is some what limited here because of the complex nature of absorption in the region $1\ 550\text{--}1\ 630\text{ cm}^{-1}$. However, the strong peak of the ligands at about $1\ 605\text{ cm}^{-1}$ registers substantial decrease in the intensity after complex formation. This band may be assigned to complex vibration involving $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$, δ_{NH_2} and the benzene ring^{11,14}. The band due to the ligands at about $1\ 545\text{ cm}^{-1}$ probably a coupled vibration of δ_{NH} (of HNCO moiety) and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ shifts to about $1\ 515\text{ cm}^{-1}$ after complexation¹⁵. The $\nu_{\text{N}-\text{N}}$ band in the ligands observed at about $1\ 050\text{ cm}^{-1}$ shifts to about $1\ 035\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes¹⁶. Thus, it is concluded that the ligand behaves as a dibasic tridentate for the parent complexes. The band at $3\ 350\text{--}3\ 370\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the Mn^{II} and UO_2^{II} complexes shows the presence of coordinated water molecule¹⁷. Since the metal-to-ligand ratio is 1 : 1 at least dimerisation (III) is required to achieve four- and six-coordination in the complexes reported. Insoluble nature of the complexes in common organic solvents also to some extent supports the proposed dimeric structure¹⁸.

Electrical conductivity : The electrical conductivity of the ligands and their metal chelates was studied over a wide range of temperature. The electrical conductivity (σ) varies exponentially

Where R = o-Cl (OAOCATS), p-Cl (OAPCATS)

X and X' are absent when
 $\text{M} = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}, \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}$
 X and X' = $\text{H}_2\text{O}^{\text{II}}$ when
 $\text{M} = \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}, \text{UO}_2^{\text{II}}$

with the absolute temperature according to the relationship $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp -E_a/kT$, where σ is the conductivity at T (K), σ_0 the specific conductivity, E_a the activation energy and k the Boltzman constant. The activation energy decreases in the order : $\text{Co} > \text{Zn} > \text{OAOCATS} > \text{UO}_2 > \text{Mn} > \text{Cd} > \text{Ni} > \text{Hg}$ and $\text{OAPCATS} > \text{Zn} > \text{Ni} > \text{Co} > \text{UO}_2 > \text{Cd} > \text{Hg} > \text{Mn}$, which is in partial agreement with reported results¹⁹.

Thermal study : The examination of the results of TG and DSC (Table 2) reveals that the metal chelates follow a single step decomposition. From TG traces it is observed that the curves for metal chelates are steeper while the curve for the ligand is broader. On this basis it is assumed that the rate of reaction for the metal chelate decomposition is faster than that of the ligand. The Broido method was applied to TG data to determine the energy of activation and the order of the reaction²⁰. The two water molecules in the Mn^{II} and UO_2^{II} complexes were lost at around 160° , indicating that these molecules are coordinated to the respective metal ion²¹. The trend in thermal stability of the metal chelates on the basis of E_a values follows the decreasing order : $\text{OAOCATS} > \text{Zn} > \text{UO}_2 > \text{Ni} > \text{Mn} > \text{Cd} > \text{Hg} > \text{Co}$ and $\text{OAPCATS} > \text{Zn} > \text{UO}_2 > \text{Mn} > \text{Ni} > \text{Hg} > \text{Cd} > \text{Co}$. From DSC traces, it is observed that single step decomposition of the ligands and the metal com-

TABLE 2—TG AND DSC DATA OF THE LIGANDS AND THEIR CHELATES

Compd.	TG				DSC			
	T_s °C	T_E °C	Weight loss %	Activation energy (E) kcal mol ⁻¹	T_s °C	T_E °C	Peak temp. °C	ΔH J g ⁻¹
OAOCATS	225	370	77.0	6.22	225	280	270	28.55
[Ni-OAOCATS]	320	410	51.0	4.80	335	390	378	54.18
[Co-OAOCATS]	260	350	48.0	3.48	265	305	291	40.27
[Zn-OAOCATS]	300	380	45.5	5.54	280	320	291	75.00
					325	375	356	16.72
[Mn-(OAOCATS).2H ₂ O]	225	315	53.0	4.39	245	300	286	38.63
[Cd-OAOCATS]	260	340	55.0	3.91	280	325	308	35.00
[Hg-OAOCATS]	250	345	50.0	3.53	270	325	309	25.44
[UO ₂ -(OAOCATS).2H ₂ O]	240	350	62.0	5.24	290	340	330	30.00
OAPCATS	205	335	74.0	6.31	215	270	255	27.91
[Ni-OAPCATS]	290	370	51.0	3.94	300	350	342	51.54
[Co-OAPCATS]	250	295	46.0	3.47	255	295	284	45.03
[Zn-OAPCATS]	315	395	44.0	5.53	305	350	338	59.31
					365	380	361	19.19
[Mn-(OAPCATS).2H ₂ O]	230	310	53.0	4.28	235	310	289	29.38
[Cd-OAPCATS]	235	355	55.0	3.67	235	345	331	35.11
[Hg-OAPCATS]	265	325	59.0	3.83	250	310	300	39.43
[UO ₂ -(OAPCATS).2H ₂ O]	270	425	62.0	4.68	310	365	356	26.09

plexes takes place as they show the presence of single exothermic peak. However, in the Zn^{II} chelate a complex exothermic peak is present in all the traces. The reason for this is that the Zn chelate is thermally most stable with high E_a involved in its decomposition process. The metal chelates under study do not undergo any observable physical or chemical changes before their thermal decomposition. The loss of two water molecules is noticed by the presence of endothermic peak in the Mn^{II} and UO₂^{II} traces.

Antimicrobial activities : The ligands OAOCATS, OAPCATS and their metal chelates were studied for their antimicrobial activity towards *E. coli*, *P. fluorescens*, *S. marcescens*, *B. subtilis*, *A. niger* and *T. longibrachiatum*. *Ortho*- and *para*-chloroanilide ligands showed inhibitory effects on the growth of test organisms. Remarkable inhibition of *E. coli* and *S. marcescens* was noticed (40–50%) with OAOCATS and OAPCATS ligands respectively. Inactivation of antimicrobial properties upon chelation may be due to structural changes in functional group responsible for antimicrobial action. None of the metal chelates enhanced the antimicrobial effects of the ligands. The metal chelates (Ni, Cd and Hg) of OAOCATS and OAPCATS did show antimicrobial effect. However,

this may be due to inhibitory nature of Ni, Cd and Hg. The ligands showed strong inhibitory effect with 40–50% growth towards *A. niger* and *T. longibrachiatum*.

Present studies thus indicate that the metal chelates of polydentate ligands containing thiosemicarbazone function are capable of exhibiting antimicrobial effect which can vary with organisms as well as the metal ion.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The ligands (OAOCATS and OAPCATS) were synthesised by the known method²².

The Ni^{II} complexes : To the ligand OAOCATS (0.010 mol) dissolved in ethanol (100 ml), was added an aqueous solution (50 ml) of nickel(II) acetate monohydrate (0.005 mol) whereby a brown coloured product separated out. The mixture was digested on a water-bath for 1 h. The resulting solid was washed with hot distilled water, ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. The yield was quantitative. The corresponding Co, Mn, Zn, Hg, Cd and UO₂ complexes of OAOCATS and OAPCATS ligands were synthesised by the same method. All the complexes were found insoluble in common organic solvents.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer and diffuse reflectance spectra on a Beckman DK-2A spectrophotometer using MgO as a reference material. Magnetic studies were made at room temperature by Gouy method using mercurytetrathiocyanatocobalt(II) as a calibrant. Metal estimations were carried out by standard methods²³. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method and sulphur by fusion method²⁴. The TG and DSC thermograms were scanned on a Du-Pont 951 and 900 thermal analyzer respectively. The electrical conductivity was measured over a wide range of temperature in air using a Hewlett-Packard 4329 A high resistance meter.

Pregrown cultures of the bacteria and fungi were inoculated into N-Broth and Sabouraud's dextrose medium respectively. Activities of bacteria were estimated by measuring growth after 48 h using a Systronic digital spectrophotometer at 660 nm. The experiment was carried out with and without sample (500 ppm). Activities of fungi on samples (750 ppm) were determined by measuring growth after 96 h. The growth was determined as dry cell mass.

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